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SMART CITY AS AN ALTERNATIVE SOLUTION FOR URBAN DEVELOPMENT AND EQUITY IN INDONESIA

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AGRO.IT (Agro Innovation And Technology): IoT integrated smart farming system based on optimization of state agricultural land and renewable energy in improving sustainable agricultural product commodities

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Abstract. The application of multidisciplinary innovation is needed in solving problems in society, one of which is collaboration using IoT technology in agro-industry, with smart farming architectural designs. Agricultural monitoring systems in the digital era use artificial intelligence. This research is quantitative, and the data obtained through literature study using an empirical study approach Monitoring is carried out through planting different agricultural and horticultural commodities for each stage on the farming land floor. Sensors are used in agricultural land work to determine soil chemical conditions, soil moisture, plant health quality, and other related information to optimize agricultural yields. AGRO.IT and its mobile application design utilize big data technology, machine learning, robotics, and IoT to improve the farm industry's quality and quantity of production in integrated agricultural monitoring applications with gadgets on terraced land for agricultural and horticultural commodities. Components in smart Farming automate agricultural activities by minimizing emissions to the environment. Solar thermal energy sources are stored in solar panels as energy reserves converted into mechanical energy sources for automatic watering, automatic irrigation, and energy reserves to create a lighting system in a system with minimal lighting, in addition to the primary source of electrical energy. IoT- integrated Smart Farming and optimization of renewable energy are seen as the future of sustainable agriculture. It produces optimal farmer yields with efficient resources and is easy to operate with a digital approach. Smart Farming will encourage the achievement of community food and nutrition targets sustainably and sustainably through farmer empowerment.

Keywords: IoT, Multilevel Agricultural Land, Monitoring, Renewable energy, Smart Farming.

1. Introduction

The Industrial Revolution 5.0 has entered various industrial sectors. In this era has begun to use information technology to support business and company activities by using the development of information technology. However, technological developments must be able to improve the welfare of human life. Indonesia's overall readiness to implement the Industrial revolution still has to be considered with the current conditions of the Industrial revolution 4.0.

To face the Industrial revolution that is developing towards a more advanced direction, the provisions that prepare are from adaptive human resources with the ability to think analytically, critically, and creatively. Based on data obtained from the Central Statistics Agency and the Directorate

General of Horticulture (2019), it shows that since the last five years, the agricultural sub-sector has fluctuated in several commodities, even in addition to growth, there has also been a decline which indicates a deficit of farm products, especially in several things such as potatoes. Onions, cabbage, mustard greens, red beans, and many more. The highest growth is shown in the commodity of garlic and paprika. The condition of the land is also affected by the narrowing because much ground is converted into buildings or as housing.

As a result of changes in agricultural patterns in each location, there is a gap between increase and reduction in horticultural agricultural yields. In addition to external factors that affect conditions such as crop failure, there is inadequate education for farmers in terms of farming. Information technology can be used to optimize the potential of agricultural products to generate significant profits for farmers. Farmers who have adequate competence will increase food self-sufficiency and improve the welfare of the community itself. Communities, especially farmers, do not necessarily get sufficient education regarding the application of technology, so students as a generation with the capacity and competence in specific fields can solve real agricultural problems by integrating currently developing technologies such as the use of the Internet of Things.

IoT (Internet of Things) can be defined as the ability of various devices to connect and exchange data with each other through the internet network. IoT is a concept about everyday objects with sensors, software, or other technology, connecting them to other devices and systems via the internet. Simply, this concept aims to connect all physical objects to the internet[1]. In addition, the main factor of environmental damage is the waste or inefficient use of energy. Any use of energy that results from the destruction of all substances will become pollutants or substances detrimental to nature. Generally, the pollutants produced are hydrocarbons (HC), nitrogen oxides (NO_x), and carbon monoxide (CO)[2]. Continuously, these exhaust gases cannot be synthesized by nature and will accumulate in the ozone layer, the accumulation of these pollutants is known as Greenhouse Gases. Greenhouse gas emissions will gradually fill the atmosphere into an ozone crust that can hold heat out of the atmosphere. The accumulated heat will accumulate and make the earth's temperature increase or called global warming (Global Warming).

This study aims to design a system Smart Farming with optimization of terraced land use and application design to monitor the process of farming agricultural and horticultural crops involving farmers and the community so that they become agrarian digitalization, with technology carried out using various sensors that will help increase crop yields, in collaboration with the design of automation of irrigation and watering technology, along with the concept of green building with a solar panel roof as a source of solar energy storage.

2. Research Methods

2.1. Data Collection Techniques

This study uses qualitative and quantitative data from various relevant literature and several existing sources and references. According to the Big Indonesian Dictionary, qualitative data is not from numbers obtained from recordings, observations, interviews, or written materials. At the same time, quantitative data can be measured or calculated directly as a variable number or number. The sources included data from the Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Indonesia as a reference and journals and books under the issues raised.

2.2. Data Analysis Techniques

The research method used is descriptive analysis. Descriptive analysis is a method of examining the status of a group of people, an object, a set of conditions, a system of thought or a class of events in the present[3]. The data to be analyzed is data sourced from literature studies. Literature study is a series of activities related to library data collection methods, reading and recording and managing research materials

2.3. Data collection methods

Used in this study is quantitative data obtained through literature study using an empirical study approach. According to the Big Indonesian Dictionary, quantitative data can be measured or calculated directly as a variable number or number. The sources used include experimental data and journals, and books that follow the issues raised.

3. Result

3.1. Innovative Farming Concept-Smart Farming

It is a technology-based innovative farming method. The technologies used in Smart Farming include drones that spray pesticides and liquid fertilizers, Drone Surveillance (Drones for land mapping) and Soil and Weather Sensors (soil and weather sensors). Precision Agriculture or precision farming makes farming practices more accurate and controlled in terms of growing crops[4]. The main component of this agricultural management approach is an information technology and various items such as GPS guidance, control systems, sensors, robotics, drones, autonomous vehicles, GPS-based soil sampling and software [5]. Wireless Sensor Network, or in many kinds of literature called Wireless Sensor Network (WSN), is a network that connects devices such as sensor nodes, routers and sinks nodes. These devices are connected on an ad-hoc basis and support multi-hop communication. The term ad-hoc refers to the ability of machines to communicate with each other directly without the need for network infrastructures such as routers or access points[6].

The lack of existing agricultural land can be optimized with the condition of using terraced land for agriculture. Prevention of the effects of global warming is to optimize renewable energy sources that are environmentally friendly. Carbon dioxide or CO₂ is the most influential gas in increasing the greenhouse effect. In 1994, 83% of the increase in greenhouse gas radiation was caused by CO₂, 15% by methane and the rest by N₂O, NO_x and CO[7].

AGRO.IT is an intelligent farming concept that integrates IoT in hybrid agriculture and the design of mobile apps utilizing technology in the form of integrated agricultural monitoring applications with gadgets on terraced land for agricultural and horticultural commodities. Components in smart farming automate agricultural activities by minimizing emission output to the environment. Solar thermal energy sources are stored in solar panels as energy reserves, converted into mechanical energy sources for automatic watering machines, automatic irrigation, automatic fertilization, and energy reserves to create a lighting system in a system with minimal lighting other than the primary source of electrical energy.

3.2. Novelty of Ideas

A novelty in this system is the application of farming patterns that can be varied by farmers, with a vertically terraced land system to the top. Still, the building design follows the green building concept with the application of automatic irrigation systems, monitoring, and solar panels for sources. Energy reserves. The monitoring feature functions as a monitoring of the sensors used in the IoT system. Sensors are devices used to detect changes in physical quantities such as pressure, force, electrical quantities, light, motion, humidity, temperature, speed and other environmental phenomena. After observing the change, the detected input will be converted into output that can be understood by humans either through the sensor device itself or transmitted electronically through the network to be displayed or processed into helpful information for its users. Sensors can be classified as input transducers because they can convert physical energy such as light, pressure, motion, temperature or other physical energy into electrical signals or resistance (converted back to voltage or electrical signals) (M Simanjuntak, 2020). This is also in line with how solar panels can store electrical energy reserves, converted into energy sources.

3.3. The Advantages of the System

The advantages of this system are that monitoring agricultural land is easier to do; rural yields will increase further, users can use it quickly because the features in the application are easy to understand

for farmers, and farmers can find out information on the state of the land from the plants being planted. . With an attractive and easy user interface, it will make optimal use of the application and will have an impact on increasing foreign exchange in the agricultural sector on a macro basis if dissemination is carried out.

3.4. Prototype of AGRO.IT

The whole system involves various systems through an automated approach to the interaction of artificial and human systems through computer control that adjusts several hardware and software components. The operating system that works is to provide input or data input to obtain output in the form of activities that automatically run according to the instructions in the operating system.

Figure 1 Schemesystem of implementation

Monitoring Carried out by farmers through controls on android, with land that has been installed with various IoT-integrated sensors that show the performance of Smart Farming. The AGRO.IT application will display the incoming monitoring data to the farmer's cellphone through the database recorded on the microcontroller; the sensor will work according to its function in measuring and monitoring various existing indicators. The output is in the form of notifications, and suggestions to adjust to the object's state is observed.

Figure 2 The application flowchart

Sensors working on AGRO.IT function to generate digital signals, WSN to collect readings on various sensors, Arduino Mega microcontrollers are used to process data, and in the form of an ethernet

shield is used to send data to the application database and can show monitoring data into infographics in the application[8][9]

Figure 3 The application User Interface

Sensors involved include PH Meter Sensors, EC Sensors, Temperature. Sensors, DO Sensors, Flow Sensors, CO2 Sensors, Dew Point Sensors, and Soil Moisture Sensors. Land use is made of terraces with different plant variations at each level, and the database will be recorded first as characteristics testing the monitoring process. Solar panels will be located on the roof with a transparent building, accompanied by an IoT-based irrigation system integrated with a sensor system for measuring water levels.

Figure 4 Agricultural Land Design

Figure 5 Verticulture Display: Terracing of land for each stage

3.5. Dissemination program

The process of disseminating innovation is carried out by preparing work guidelines, socialization, discussion and question and answer, and skills training, mentoring and evaluation. The preparation of work guidelines is carried out for one month, including starting farming system guidelines. Socialization is the primary method in implementing this program. Each farmer will be demonstrated directly about the equipment that has been developed and at the same time how to manufacture each equipment. Problems related to farming techniques and monitoring with applications are resolved through discussion forums and questions and answers. For the continuity of the transfer of farming skills, farmers are allowed to practice the activities. After the socialization activities are completed, mentoring activities will continue to be carried out, where the success of the dissemination process will be reviewed continuously and evaluated.

4. Conclusion

The application of AGRO.IT can be an appropriate technology to realize an intelligent farming system that integrates IoT to optimize agricultural products. IoT-based technology with the use of rural digitization can become a parameter of adaptive ability in the face of the Industrial Revolution 5.0 for the advancement of national food security.

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